

Enhancing Medical Image Analysis: A Pipeline Combining Synthetic Image Generation and Super-Resolution

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Abstract. Cancer is a leading cause of mortality worldwide, with breast and lung cancer being the most prevalent globally. Early and accurate diagnosis is crucial for successful treatment, and medical imaging techniques play a pivotal role in achieving this. This paper proposes a novel pipeline that leverages generative artificial intelligence to enhance medical images by combining synthetic image generation and super-resolution techniques. The framework is validated in two medical use cases (breast and lung cancers), demonstrating its potential to improve the quality and quantity of medical imaging data, ultimately contributing to more precise and effective cancer diagnosis and treatment. Overall, although some limitations do exist, this paper achieved satisfactory results for an image size which is conducive to specialist analysis, and further expands upon this field’s capabilities.

Keywords: breast cancer · deep learning · image super-resolution · lung cancer · medical image analysis · synthetic image generation

1 Introduction

Cancer is a disease that occurs by a series of successive mutations in genes, provoking changes in cell functions. It is one of the leading causes of mortality worldwide, being a serious problem that affects the health of all humans. The prevalence of cancer varies between men (the most common are prostate, lung and bronchus, colon and rectum, and urinary bladder) and women (the most common are breast, lung and bronchus, colon and rectum, uterine corpus and thyroid) [9], with breast and lung as the most prevalent cancers globally. While early and accurate diagnoses play a pivotal role in the success of cancer treatment, medical imaging techniques (e.g., computed tomography (CT), magnetic

resonance imaging (MRI) or radiography) are crucial in the precision and quality of those diagnoses. Naturally, the availability of medical imaging data is critical to the quality and predictive performance of machine learning algorithms for healthcare applications. Generative artificial intelligence (AI) can play a relevant role in this matter, given its ability to produce new data points by sampling from the (learned) model distribution [16]. In this paper, we build on top of the state-of-the-art generative AI models and propose a pipeline that combines synthetic image generation and super-resolution to enhance medical images. The aim of this combination is to split the task into two: anatomical coherence and variability is handled by the generative portion, while higher quality and fine detail building can be attributed to super-resolution. We validate our framework in two medical use cases (breast and lung cancer), discuss its advantages and current limitations, and suggest future work directions in this field of research. The code related to this work is publicly available in a GitHub repository⁵.

2 Background and State of the Art

2.1 Clinical Context: Breast and Lung Cancers

Breast cancer is a disease in which abnormal breast cells grow out of control and form tumours, which can spread throughout the body and become fatal if not detected. This disease occurs in every country in the world, and approximately half of all breast cancers occur in women with no specific risk factors other than sex and age. The treatment may consist of surgery, radiation therapy and medications, and depends on the individual, the cancer type and its spread [23]. **Lung cancer** is a type of cancer that starts when abnormal cells grow in an uncontrolled way in the lungs. It is often diagnosed at advanced stages when treatment options are limited, becoming a serious health issue that can cause severe harm and death. The most common types of lung cancer are non-small cell carcinoma (more common and grows slowly) and small cell carcinoma (less common but often grows quickly). The key to improving survival rates relies on the early detection and screening of high-risk individuals. Besides, primary prevention (e.g., tobacco control measures and reducing exposure to environmental risk factors) can also minimise incidence [24].

2.2 Synthesis of Medical Image Data

In the past years, deep generative models (e.g., convolutional neural networks (CNNs), diffusion models, generative adversarial networks (GANs), variational autoencoders (VAEs)) proved to be an interesting tool for 2D and 3D medical image synthesis, showing their potential in a diverse range of clinically relevant applications (e.g., image generation, image-to-image translation, or image reconstruction) [5]. In this section, we highlight several generative models under the scope of this work (and used in our experiments). Kwon et al. [11] proposed the

⁵ https://github.com/brightside51/IbPRIA2025_Medical_GenSR_Pipeline

3D Wasserstein GAN (3D WGAN), a GAN-based model architecture for 3D inputs, optimised with the Wasserstein distance to promote stability and reliable convergence, and using a critic model as a discriminator to score the realness of the generated samples. Later, Gulrajani et al. [7] extended the latter and released the **WGAN-GP**, which uses gradient penalty (instead of weight clipping) to stabilise the training loop and increase the model’s convergence speed. These architectures also benefit from an extra hyperparameter, α , a regularisation term in the loss function that controls the quality of the generated samples (we refer to these variations as 3D α -WGAN and 3D α -WGAN-GP). Finally, Sun et al. [18] developed the **3D Hierarchical Amortised GAN** (3D HA-GAN), that focused on solving the memory limitations related to generating realistic and high-quality 3D images by using multiple resolution hierarchical framework and dissipating the workload between various levels, while still maintaining global and local structural details, and through the introduction of *amortised inference*, which allows for better control and efficiency in the sampling process by allowing the generator to learn a structured latent space conditioned on hierarchical features (and reducing the risk of anatomically non-plausible structures).

2.3 Enhancement of Medical Image Data

Image super-resolution (ISR) is a technique used to enhance the quality of an image, usually increasing its original size [25]. In ISR, the goal is to create a high-resolution (HR) version of a low-resolution (LR) image by predicting the missing information that naturally results from this transformation. The first approaches to ISR involved traditional computer vision techniques (e.g., interpolation [8]) that relied on predefined algorithms to increase image size and quality. Naturally, advances in deep learning allowed the training of CNNs [4] and GANs [13] on large image datasets to achieve enhanced ISR. The state-of-the-art comprises two groups of ISR strategies: *supervised*, applicable to scenarios of relatively high data availability, consists of optimising the models with paired LR-HR images (i.e., LR images as the inputs and HR images as the ground-truth labels); and *unsupervised*, ideal for scenarios with relatively low data availability, consists of optimising the models with unpaired LR-HR images [22]. Regarding the CNN [1,4,12,27] vs. GAN [13,20,21] dichotomy, we observe that there is no clear gold standard for ISR, as performance will naturally varies with the application. For instance, in the medical domain, most of the ISR strategies described in the literature derive from deep learning approaches. Moreover, it is relevant to recall that, in this domain, there is an extra challenge motivated by the diverse medical imaging modalities (e.g., X-ray, computed tomography (CT), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)) that have specific intrinsic properties, that might create additional constraints when developing and optimising methods tailored for a specific use case. Umehara et al. [19] and Park et al. [15] applied CNN-based architectures to CT images of the chest and brain, respectively, and reported increased performances against computer vision methods. Mansoor et al. [14] and You et al. [26] explored the use of GAN-based approaches for CT and MRI imaging, introducing novel regularisation and data augmentation methods to

achieve stabilised training with robust results. Moreover, given its relevancy in this work, we point the reader to the work of Wang et al. [20], which proposed the **Real Enhanced Super-Resolution GAN** (Real-ESRGAN), a model that extends two works (i.e., Ledig et al. [13] and Wang et al. [21]), and introduced a discriminator module that relatively compares synthetic/non-synthetic images, using perceptual losses to stabilise the training.

3 Methodology

3.1 Datasets

In this work, we used two medical use cases (breast and lung cancers) and different imaging techniques (CT and MRI). For the **breast cancer** use case, we used two MRI data collections: 768 T1-weighted images from the *Duke-Breast-Cancer-MRI* [17], a publicly available dataset which includes high-quality 3D samples for 922 patients diagnosed with invasive breast cancer collected in between 2000 and 2014; and an aggregation of 89 3D volumes acquired within the scope of the *BCCT.plan* project in partnership with the Champalimaud Foundation. For the **lung cancer** use case, we used two CT data collections: the *Lung Image Database Consortium and Image Database Resource Initiative* (LIDC/IDRI) dataset [2], which is made up of 1018 thoracic CT scans collected from 7 academic institutions, with both cancer-suffering and healthy patients; and the *Reference Image Database to Evaluate Therapy Response* (RIDER) dataset [3], which consists of about 15000 CT scans from 32 different patients (only used in ISR models). Regarding pre-processing, we applied a min-max normalisation to all the images, adjusted the Hounsfield unit range to $[-1000, 400]$, and resized all the 2D samples of the 3D volumes to 64^3 and 128^3 .

3.2 Models: Synthetic Image Generation and Super-Resolution

For the task of synthetic image generation, we optimised three generative models, **3D WGAN**, **3D α -WGAN**, and **3D HA-GAN**, and for the task of super-resolution, we trained a **Real-ESRGAN** (see section 2 for more information).

3.3 Performance Evaluation

Assessing the performance of generative models is a crucial aspect of understanding their capabilities and limitations that go beyond the traditional quantitative metrics (e.g., **mean absolute error** (MAE), **mean squared error** (MSE)). Hence, we must address perceptual measures (that try to mimic human perception by exploring a more holistic and high-level comparison, unlike pixel-wise methods) and the feedback of human experts [5]. For the purpose of our work, we highlight: the **Structural Similarity Index** (SSIM) and **Multi-Scale Structural Similarity Index** (MS-SSIM), which compare two samples by considering the luminance, contrast and structure (MS-SSIM computes these across multiple

scales and can also be used to assess the diversity of a given sample population by comparing its value to that of similar subsets); the **Inception Score** (IS) and **Mode Score** (MS), which combine the need for high specificity shown by low entropy in conditional label distributions and high diversity proven by high entropy in marginal distributions (higher IS and MS values will therefore denote a more diverse set of high-quality generated images); the **Fréchet Inception Distance** (FID), which calculates the Fréchet distance between the fake and real multivariate Gaussian distributions, meaning that lower FIDs are preferable (pre-trained FID computation models usually compare given samples to datasets of non-synthetic data); **Peak Signal to Noise Ratio** (PSNR) as a way of quantifying similarity and distortion between images and their super-resolution counterparts; and the **Maximum Mean Discrepancy** (MMD), which quantifies the discrepancy between two probability distributions and their feature means in the higher-dimensional reproducing kernel Hilbert space. Additionally, as the ultimate assessment metric, we conducted a **Visual Turing Test** (VTT) [6] (i.e., a series of binary questions to assess the capacity for object recognition and discernment of the characteristics between images) with two board-certified radiologists. In our work, we selected random 128^3 synthetic and non-synthetic data and asked the radiologists to answer whether these were fake or not. To avoid bias, we ensure that each group of images shown to the experts had no more than 60% of synthetic/non-synthetic images. The confusion matrix was then drawn for assessment of the results.

3.4 Experimental Protocol

A number of different experiments were setup for the generative models, which will be described in this section. The sizes chosen for final generated samples were 64^3 and 128^3 , although HA-GAN only handled the higher resolution. It should be noted that, as a way of evaluating the efficiency of the adversarial training method, this project kept breast MRI as a control group and executed lung CT generation in two different manners: experiment #1 included updating the generator and discriminator once per iteration; experiment #2, had a 5-1 update-per-iteration ratio in the direction of the generator, in order to investigate if more updating would allow the generator to create better fake volumes and prevent the occurrence of discriminator overfitting or mode collapse.

As for the super-resolution model, we have chosen to perform experiments using both each imaging modality (breast MRI and lung CT images) separately and the two modalities together. By testing the latter on each of the imaging technique datasets and on a combination of the two, one can assess the model’s ability to generalise between different imaging modes and body parts. Rather than attempting a simpler 2x size augmentation, all depicted experiments focus on 4x super-resolution, which will then be compared to one another and to the standard method of bicubic interpolation. After various iterations, the final Real-ESRGAN training method and the one to perform the best included fine-tuning and the introduction of heavy blurring into real low-resolution samples, so as to lessen the quality gap between these and synthetic images.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Breast MRI Generative Task

For lower resolutions WGAN struggles a lot with tissue constitution, leading to a number of deformities and artifacts, which α -WGAN is not so prone to. These two models display the expected increased blurriness and artifact presence at a higher resolution. HA-GAN, on the other hand, even despite having less training iterations and some peripheral missing information, seems to perform the best, indicating the efficiency of adding local high-resolution patches. Examples of these results and their quality are provided in Fig. 1.

Breast MRI Qualitative Results	64^3 Resolution		128^3 Resolution	
	Middle	Peripheral	Middle	Peripheral
3D WGAN-GP				
3D α -WGAN-GP				
Real Dataset / HA-GAN				

Fig. 1: Qualitative results comprised of a middle and peripheral slice of synthetic 3D breast MRI volumes created by all 3 proposed models for both 64^3 and 128^3 size experiments. Rather than 64^3 -sized scans created by HA-GAN (which were not tested), the **bottom left corner** includes a middle slices of two real data samples (with sizes 64^3 on the left and 128^3 on the right) for comparison.

These results are largely verified by those of Table 1. Considering the use of similar training conditions, we conclude that HA-GAN generated samples' distribution and diversity are closest to those of the real dataset. At lower image sizes, α -WGAN proves the benefits of latent space modelling seeing as it reduces blurriness and mode collapse. While similar MS-SSIM values do not guarantee sample quality, it does attest to the model's ability to match real data variability. It should also be stated that the FID metric can be somewhat unreliable for the evaluation of medical imaging results [10], especially if its model is not trained on such data as is the case for this study.

Table 1: Quantitative metric results of all 3 proposed models for both 64^3 and 128^3 resolution experiments. Metrics include the FID value computed for 100 artificial 3D samples, as well as MMD and MS-SSIM values for 100 artificial-real 3D sample pairs. \Leftrightarrow symbolises that the best value is that which is closest to the real dataset’s.

Breast MRI	64^3 Size			128^3 Size		
	FID ↓	MMD ↓	MS-SSIM \Leftrightarrow	FID ↓	MMD ↓	MS-SSIM \Leftrightarrow
3D WGAN-GP	187.3	28560.8	0.522	211.9	220148.8	0.399
3D α-WGAN-GP	172.9	26437.4	0.484	166.6	201911.4	0.476
HA-GAN	-	-	-	189.7	200879.9	0.414
Real Dataset	-	-	0.402	-	-	0.389

4.2 Lung CT Generative Task

Fig. 2: Qualitative results comprised of slices of synthetic 3D lung CT volumes created by all 3 proposed models for both 64^3 and 128^3 size experiments and for each of the two experiments performed. Rather than 64^3 -sized scans created by HA-GAN (which were not tested), the **bottom left corner** includes a middle slices of two real data samples (with sizes 64^3 on the left and 128^3 on the right) for comparison. On the right, slices of unrealistic and faulty samples created by each model may also be found.

Even though major structures were outlined, lower image-size samples suffer from lack of definition regarding other minor airways and pulmonary vessels. As for the differences between both WGAN models, these mostly revolve around colour saturation and texture quality. The WGAN model also showed signs of having suffered mode collapse, seeing as different artificial samples would be almost identical, regardless of the randomly initialised noise vector. For higher resolution samples, there is a noticeable increase in detail and the outlining of minor structures, such as the ribcage, as well as a greater abundance of unwanted

artifacts. In the case of α -WGAN, one can consider the existence of some degree of overfitting, displayed by the greyish background of synthetic samples which is also present on some of the training samples. HA-GAN performed the best, detailing both major and minor structures in clear detail. Overall, and as can be ascertained by the examples of Fig. 2, the second experiments performed better, namely for higher resolutions, leading one to believe that more often generator updates does indeed result in better fake volumes by pushing the discriminator’s capabilities further.

Table 2: Quantitative metric results of all 3 proposed models for both 64^3 and 128^3 size experiments and also the number of the experiment which obtained the best results. Metrics include the FID value computed for 100 artificial 3D samples, as well as MMD and MS-SSIM values for 100 artificial-real 3D sample pairs. \Leftrightarrow symbolises that the best value is that which is closest to the real dataset’s and * indicates that MMD has been normalised and is now in the order of 10^{-4} .

Lung CT	64^3 Size				128^3 Size			
	FID \downarrow	*MMD \downarrow	MS-SSIM \Leftrightarrow	Exp.	FID \downarrow	*MMD \downarrow	MS-SSIM \Leftrightarrow	Exp.
3D WGAN-GP	189.4	3.48	0.997	1	178.6	16.84	0.431	2
3D α-WGAN-GP	149.2	3.62	0.437	1	296.8	87.00	0.305	2
HA-GAN	-	-	-	-	156.1	30.86	0.337	1
Real Dataset	-	-	0.325	-	-	-	0.325	-

Quantitatively, we have chosen to display the results of Table 2 according to the better experiment, with MMD values having a large discrepancy from those of the breast MRI section simply because of a normalisation factor. A high-level analysis of these results somewhat disproves some of the visual conclusions, once again indicating that perceptual metrics do not always match human understanding. The first example of this phenomenon comes from lower image resolution samples, in which the first experiment seems to achieve the best results for both WGAN models. On the other hand, WGAN is confirmed to suffer from mode collapse and very poor sample variety given the almost perfect 64^3 MS-SSIM score. At higher resolutions, experiments seem to agree that repeated updates of the generator’s weights has a positive impact on performance, although MMD values increase due to the larger amount of detailed features that this image size requires. While variability may be somewhat lower than that of the real dataset, mode collapse is clearly resolved by higher image WGAN size experiments and as proven before, α -WGAN’s greyer hue and artifacts reflect onto the higher MMD and FID values. Finally, we conclude that HA-GAN is the model to perform the best both in metrics and perceptually.

4.3 Super-Resolution Task

In order to test a Real-ESRGAN model trained on two different imaging modalities, we have used samples from one single data type. The fact that its results, shown in Table 3, are superior to those of the model trained on a single image type proves the benefits of cross-modality training and that a more informed

Table 3: Quantitative metric results for all final Real-ESRGAN experiments and baseline bicubic interpolation computed by comparing real 3D 512×512 -sized lung CT and breast MRI volumes (ground truth) with a counterpart which underwent downsizing (into 128×128) and then $4 \times$ super-resolution.

Super-Resolution		Evaluation Metrics		
Training Set	Test Set	SSIM \uparrow	MMD \downarrow	PSNR \uparrow
1 Modality	1 Modality	0.81	42.2	32.0
2 Modalities	1 Modality	0.82	52.5	31.01
	2 Modalities	0.70	1143.6	23.72
Bicubic Interpolation		0.86	38.67	32.23

model will generalise better. Moreover, one can also conclude that metric values are not always the best assessment method, seeing as, despite clear perceptual improvements over the standard method such as those seen in the slices of Fig. 3, the proposed methods still fall short of bicubic interpolation’s metric values. For synthetic data, this perceptual improvement may not always be the case, but by introducing a degree of blurring we have also approximated real samples to artificial ones, closing the gap in structural quality. Despite the existence of artifacts, noise and low contrast areas, the proposed method still demonstrates the ability to increase the artificial samples’ clarity and detail.

Fig. 3: Qualitative results comprised of slices from real and Real-ESRGAN synthetic 3D lung CT and breast MRI volumes with a size of 512×512 after $4 \times$ augmentation from 128×128 . The comparison can be made between the ground truth (which the exception with synthetic data for which we have none), what is achieved using this model, and the traditional method of bicubic interpolation.

4.4 Visual Turing Test

The accuracy of the radiologists strayed slightly from the ideal 50%, equalling 71.7% for the breast radiology and 67% for the lung experiments. Both radiol-

ogists indicated hardship in assessing images with a size inferior to the medical standard and that they relied on first-basis intuition to predict the images’ origins. Excessive unnatural symmetry and some homogeneous tones in certain tissues were also pointed out as a clear sign of artificiality. Given the similarities between the numbers of false positives and false negatives, we can also conclude that the lower volume resolution has greatly challenged the radiologists’ task. However, these results and the feedback from the test prove to be invaluable in understanding the strong aspects and shortcomings of these generative methods. The remaining model hyperparameters, and the ones which achieved optimal results for each described model can be found in Table 4.

Table 4: Training hyperparameters for final breast MRI and lung CT model versions. * indicates that the learning rate was 0.0001 for all architectural components other than the discriminator, for which it was 0.0004.

Training Hyperparameters	Learning Rate	Training Iterations	Latent Dimension	Batch Size
3D WGAN-GP	0.0002	200 000	1000	4
3D α-WGAN-GP				
HA-GAN	0.0001*	80 000	1024	
Real-ESRGAN	0.0001	400 000	-	12

5 Conclusion

In this study, we have researched the use of a combination of GAN generative and super-resolution models as a means for high-quality 3D medical imaging data generation. Results show that while artificial data successfully mimics the anatomical structure and its intricacies at lower resolutions, the conversion to higher resolution is still a difficult task. Despite this, and given the analysis by radiologists, this pipeline proved to be a valuable asset in producing real-like synthetic scans, both perceptually and metric-wise. A future expansion of this work may include exploring generation at a higher resolution level using novel generative models such as diffusion models.

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